

Experiences from using formative feedback in entrepreneurship course

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Conference Key Areas: *Entrepreneurship Education, Student Engagement.*

Keywords: *Formative feedback, peerfeedback.*

ABSTRACT

Formative feedback is a valuable tool that enables educators to provide an immediate and ongoing feedback to improve the student learning [1]. Formative feedback can be done in a variety of ways and can be administered at various times during a learning process [1].

Many studies about feedback and assessment in entrepreneurship educations focus on measuring, assessing and evaluating the contribution of the entrepreneurship education to society etc. and only a few studies have focus on how the didactic question of assessment and feedback are done in entrepreneurship educations [2].

In this concept paper, we report and reflect on our experiences and learnings from implementing formative feedback as a mandatory part of an entrepreneurial introduction course. The paper builds on experiences from one course, which ran in January 2021, in June 2021 and in January 2022.

The feedback design used in this course can be categorized into three situations: (1) from student to student and (2) from student to educator, and (3) from educator to student. The purpose and outcome from using the feedback design is described and evaluated concerning further development. The discussion also includes which initiatives, we consider there are needed to support the further development and the implementation of formative feedback in entrepreneurial courses.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The didactic question of how assessment and feedback are used in entrepreneurial education are rarely described in literature. Instead the main focus is about how to measure, assess and evaluate the post-course contribution of the entrepreneurship education to society or the contributions of entrepreneurship education to students entrepreneurial attitudes or intentions [2].

In general, two types of feedback exist - summative and formative feedback. The summative feedback is the assessment for certification and the formative feedback is the assessment for immediate learning. In this concept paper the focus will be on the formative feedback. Formative feedback can be carried out in many ways and is a well-known valuable tool to improve the student learning [1]. Formative feedback can be given from one student to another student, from the student to the educator, from the educator to the student and from one educator to another educator.

The feedback from one student to another student is also called peerfeedback [3]. Peerfeedback is known to increase the amount of feedback the students receive and furthermore it is known to strengthen the students skills in giving and receiving feedback. However, as other forms for feedback, the peerfeedback needs to be instructed and supported, for example by having rubrics. One way to do the peerfeedback is to use the program Peergrade.io. The program Peergrade.io supports the assignment submission and the feedback process itself. The system provides overview of the students' activity as well as their feedback process [4].

The student's feedback to the educator is valuable data for the improvement of the course. In addition, the feedback can be used to ensure and optimize the quality of teaching and to enable the alignment between the intended goals and the actual learning [5]. Very often this feedback comes from the course evaluation performed at the end of the course. However it can also be done on a daily basis which enables for an immediately improvement of the course.

To give and receive feedback can be complicated and therefore the students need to learn how to do this to be able to do it in practice. There is therefore a need for a framework which clarify the roles and the rules regarding how to give and receive feedback. It is often the educator, who constructs this framework and sets up the criteria for the feedback, but it can also be done together with the students.

In this concept paper, we report and reflect on our experiences and learnings from the implementing of the formative feedback as a mandatory part of an experiential-based through learning entrepreneurship course. In this study, we do not have focus on the final evaluation (the summative feedback).

2 METHODOLOGY

The data are based on reflections from a three week course, which ran in January 2021 (52 students), June 2021 (22 students) and January 2022 (55 students) and were held at the Technical University of Denmark (DTU). The students came mainly from the bachelor of engineering education in Global Business Engineering with some few students from other bachelor of engineering programs at the University.

During the course the following feedback activities were carried out:

- Student to student feedback (peerfeedback) using the online program Peergrade.io
- Student to educator feedback done on a daily basis and at the end of the course
- Educator to student (individual/groups) several times during the course and final on the poster session

For the group work, the students were mixed in groups of 5-6 students by the educator. The group formation was performed based on a preference test, which the students did before the course. Students with different preferences were put together in the groups. During the course, the students worked with their own idea as an experiential process of learning through entrepreneurship. At the end of the course each group presented their solution at a poster session and documented the solution in a business report, which they submitted on the final day of the course. During the course, there were presentations and several hand-ins both as an individual and as a group.

Student to student feedback (Peerfeedback)

After the first week of the course the students handed in an individual report. The individual report concerned the entrepreneurial methods which the students had used and reflected upon. The maximum length of the report was set to five pages. The submission was done in the program Peergrade.io [4].

The peer feedback session consisted of four parts:

- 1) An introduction to the peerfeedback session and an introduction on how to give and receive feedback. Furthermore a short introduction to what constructive feedback is and how to use the feedback afterwards was given.
- 2) The peerfeedback session took place using the program Peergrade.io. The rubrics consisted of two criteria:
 - a. Mention something your classmate did well.
 - b. Mention something your classmate could improve.
- 3) After the peer feedback session each student met with the educator and reflected on the peerfeedback session.

- 4) In the final report, each students reflected on the peerfeedback session and the results (learning).

Each student had two hours to read and provide feedback to three fellow students. Afterwards each student received feedback from three other students and they had to respond to the feedback and do self reflection concerning the feedback given. Afterwards the educator read the feedbacks and had a follow up meeting with each student.

Later almost at the end of the course, there was a poster session. At this session, the groups gave feedback to each others presentations in regards to the content and the presentation itself.

Student to educator

Two types of student to educator feedback were used. At the end of the course, a survey-based questionnaire was sent to each student. This survey was carried out by the university and will not be discussed in this paper.

On a daily basis the students gave feedback to the educator. Two students volunteered to be the feedback persons for the day. The two students had to make notes during the day about the teaching material (papers, videos etc.) as well as the teaching activities like the activation of the students, the informations load etc. At the end of the day, the students and the educator sat together and the students gave feedback to the educator. On the next teaching day two other students were feedback persons for that day.

Educator to student (groups)

Several times during the course, formative feedback from educator to student (groups) were provided. This feedback was concerning the process.

The educator also provided feedback to the students after the individual report, so the students receive feedback from three fellow students and the educator with regards to their learning report (individual report).

Near the end of the course all student groups did a poster presentation. For this event the external censor was present. The student group received feedback from other groups, the censor and the educator. The feedback was given as formative feedback and the groups had the next two days to incorporate the feedback in the final report before submission.

3 RESULTS

A framework for giving and receiving feedback has been presented and the learnings and findings from using this framework will be presented here.

Student to student feedback (peerfeedback)

In this course, the student to student feedback is concerned with the entrepreneurial process and the students learning from using different entrepreneurial methods and tools. For the peerfeedback, the online program peergrade.io was used. The output of using the program peergrade.io has been described in previous paper for a similarly course [6]. The feedback from students were that they appreciated the way of giving and receiving feedback (see some statements below). However it is important to be clear about the expectations to the type of feedback. For example it should be made clear if the feedback is concerning the format of the report or the content. Therefore the framework for the student to student feedback can still be improved and in the future more introduction and clear expectation to the give and received feedback will be included to ensure a high output.

Statements from the students from the peerfeedback session:

- *“Overall, I liked the concept and I think feedback from other students is a good idea”.*

- *“Peergrade was really a good tool to improves one’s own report by both seeing how others have handled the task and but also by getting constructive feedback from others”.*

- *“I personally got a lot out of giving feedback to others as I was required to familiarize myself with the report in order to provide a good constructive feedback to the person”.*

At the poster session, each group had to provide feedback to another group concerning the content and outline of the poster presentation. The feedback was used to up date the final report. The student were very active in relation to give feedback in this session.

Student to educator

The focus for student to educator feedback is regarding the teaching activities and the teaching material. In this course, the feedback from the student to the educator is given in two ways – on a daily basis and at the end of the course. The feedback on the daily basis was informal semi-structured dialogues between the student and the educator concerning the teaching material and the teaching activities. The feedback giving on a daily basis was used to make directly changes when needed or to include extra material for the next lessons. The students were good at being volunteers and new students were giving feedback every day.

At the end of the course, the course was evaluated by a survey-based questionnaire. These evaluations were performed by the University and will not be discussed here.

Educator to student

The focus for the educator to student feedback is based on the entrepreneurial process. In this course, the feedback from educator to students are conducted several times during the course. The feedback from the educator to the students (group) with regards to entrepreneurial process is essential for the students to be able to create, to adjust and to help them to move forward with their projects.

Experiences from running these courses show that the students are actively involved in the feedback process and they positively appreciate the different ways of receiving and giving feedback. However a framework with clarify the rules and the roles for the feedback process is important to have.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

In this paper we have presented a feedback design used in an introduction course concerning entrepreneurship. The main focus in entrepreneurial education is often on the outcome of the entrepreneurial process and only rarely with focus on the didactical aspect. In this paper, we describe how feedback can be used to provide feedback between students, and between students and educators with a focus on both the entrepreneurial process and the students learning. The feedback from the educator to the students is essential for the students in entrepreneurship courses as the students projects and learning outcomes are created and modified based on the feedback they receive throughout the entrepreneurial process [2].

Our experiences show that the students appreciated feedback and they appreciate having an open dialogue about it. To have a feedback system is essential for the students learning process. But there is also a strong need to communicate to the students how the feedback is conducted and it's purpose in the particularly course.

The forms of feedback presented in this paper are all dialogue based with the aim of creating, adjusting and supporting the development of the entrepreneurial learning process and improve the teaching. However the framework for feedback can also be applied to other fields.

In this study, we have not had the possibility to conduct the educator to educator feedback. Feedback from one educator to another educator could be about having

focus on how the course is progressing and to what extent the teaching is supporting the students in their entrepreneurial process.

Based on our learnings we will continue working with the framework for feedback and make more guidelines regarding how to give and to receive feedback.

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